

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Phenylalanine and Serine by Chloramine-T

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Oxidation of phenylalanine and serine by chloramine-T in alkaline media has been investigated. The proposed mechanism involves two schemes. The first is followed by the major fraction of the reaction and proceeds through the interaction between α -amino acid molecule and *p*-toluenesulphochloramide in a slow and rate determining step resulting in the formation of an intermediate which subsequently attacks another molecule of *p*-toluenesulphochloramide in a fast step yielding the products. The second involves a minor fraction of the reaction in which hypochlorite ion replaces *p*-toluenesulphochloramide in the above steps. The schemes interpret the observed data satisfactorily. Various thermodynamic parameters have been computed and nitriles identified as the end products.

OXIDATIVE studies involving the less familiar redox titrant chloramine-T has been a subject of several recent studies¹⁻¹⁰. The present work constitutes an investigation on the oxidation of two α -amino acids viz., phenylalanine and serine by chloramine-T in alkaline media and a suitable mechanism subsequently formulated.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of highest purity available. Chloramine-T (E. Merck, pro analysi) solution was stored in black coated bottles to avoid photochemical effect.¹¹ Fluka AG Buchs SG sample of phenylalanine and Koch-Light (England) sample of serine were employed. All other reagents viz., sodium perchlorate, sodium chloride and methanol were of AnalaR grade. Triple distilled water was used throughout the course of investigation. Reaction stills were coated black from outside and a Leeds and Northrup pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Progress of the reaction was monitored by estimating unconsumed chloramine-T iodometrically¹². Five mls. aliquots of the reaction mixture were quickly transferred at regular intervals of time to titrating flasks containing five mls. each of 2*N* hydrochloric acid and 20% potassium iodide. Unconsumed chloramine-T liberated an equivalent amount of iodine and the latter estimated by standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator.

Results

Data compiled from several sets of experiments with varying ratios of chloramine-T to amino acid under experimental conditions for 48 hrs showed that

one mole of amino acid consumes two moles of chloramine-T according to the stoichiometric equation :

where R represents $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$ - and HOCH_2 - for phenylalanine and serine respectively. The product nitriles were tested by spot test method.¹³

"A drop of the solution of the sample is mixed in a micro test tube with some grams of manganese dioxide and the solvent is evaporated. Then the tube covered with a disc of filter paper moistened with copper acetate benzidine acetate solution, is placed in a glycerol bath preheated to 120°, the positive result is indicated by the formation of a blue stain on the filter paper".

The kinetic investigations were carried out at several initial concentrations of the reactants, keeping other variable parameters constant (Table 1). Owing to high pH, no buffer could be employed. Pseudo-first order dependence in chloramine-T was followed at all initial concentrations of the reactants (Fig. 1). The pseudo-first order rate constants were computed from the slopes of the log concentration-time plots.

A linear increase in pseudo-first order rate constant (k'_1) in chloramine-T was observed with increase in amino acid concentration. The average values of the second order rate constant calculated as $k'_2 = k'_1/[\alpha\text{-amino acid}]$ were found as 1.27 ± 0.01 , 1.46 ± 0.12 and 1.08 ± 0.08 , $1.35 \pm 0.05 \times 10^{-4}$ l.mol.⁻¹ sec.⁻¹ at 40°, 45°, for phenylalanine and serine respectively.

The reaction was found to be very susceptible to change in pH of the medium. Keeping ionic strength constant, an increase in pH considerably retarded the

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Fig. 1. First order rate plot at 40° [α -Amino acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$, pH = 11.50^a, 11.10^b [Chloramine-T] = 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.4, 2.0 and $3.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ in A, B, C, D, E and F respectively. ^a represents Phenylalanine and ^b represents Serine.

reaction rate. The order in hydroxide ion concentration calculated from the slope of the plot of $\log k'_1$

TABLE I. EFFECT OF REACTANTS' CONCENTRATION ON THE REACTION RATE.

10^3 [Chloramine-T] M	10^2 [α -Amino acid] M	$k'_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ for			
		Phenylalanine ^a		Serine ^b	
		40°	45°	40°	45°
0.6	1.0	11.3	14.2	10.7	13.2
0.8	1.0	12.2	14.5	10.8	13.0
1.0	1.0	12.8	15.2	11.2	13.4
1.4	1.0	12.3	15.5	11.5	14.3
2.0	1.0	12.4	15.8	11.5	14.5
3.0	1.0	13.0	15.9	11.7	14.7
1.0	0.6	7.67	9.16	6.97	8.50
1.0	0.8	10.3	12.8	9.21	11.2
1.0	1.4	18.1	21.1	15.4	18.4
1.0	2.0	25.6	28.3	20.3	26.0
1.0	3.0	38.0	40.2	30.7	39.4

^a pH = 11.50, ^b pH = 11.10.

against pH (Fig. 2) was found to be -0.94 , -0.96 and -0.96 , -0.98 at 40°, 45° for phenylalanine and serine respectively thereby establishing a near inverse first order dependence of the rate of hydroxide ion concentration.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k'_1$ against pH. [Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, [α -Amino acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$, Ionic strength = 0.04M.

Effect of ionic strength variations by using sodium perchlorate and sodium chloride were negligible (Table 2). The reaction was however found to have

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE REACTION RATE.

[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, [α -Amino acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$, Temperature = 40°

10 [Salt] M	$k'_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ for			
	Phenylalanine ^a		Serine ^b	
	Sodium Perchlorate	Sodium Chloride	Sodium Perchlorate	Sodium Chloride
0.0	12.8	12.8	11.2	11.2
2.0	11.9	12.2	11.5	11.5
2.8	12.1	12.1	11.5	11.6
4.0	12.0	12.0	11.6	11.6
4.8	12.0	11.9	11.6	11.7
6.0	12.1	12.1	11.5	11.5

^a pH = 11.50, ^b pH = 11.10

a little positive dielectric effect as a slight decrease in the reaction rate on increasing methanol concentration was observed (Table 3).

From the rate study measurements carried out at five temperatures, values of the thermodynamic parameters viz., energy of activation ($\Delta E^\ddagger$), frequency

TABLE 3. EFFECT OF METHANOL ON THE REACTION RATE.

[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, [α -Amino acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$,
Temperature = 40°

MeOH %	$k' \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ for	
	Phenylalanine ^a	Serine ^b
0	12.8	11.2
10	10.3	8.85
20	8.99	8.40
30	8.28	7.45
40	7.68	7.06
50	6.89	6.40

^a pH = 11.50, ^b pH = 11.10

factor (A'), entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$), heat of activation ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) and free energy of activation ($\Delta F^\ddagger$) were calculated (Table 4).

The hydrolytic steps may be shown as follows :

In an alkaline media, dichloramine-T does not exist (eq. 5). Thus chloramine-T, *p*-toluenesulphochloramide and hypochlorite ion could be the possible active oxidising species. Out of these three, *p*-toluenesulphochloramide is the only species whose relative concentration decreases with an increase in pH (or hydroxide ion concentration). As the reaction

TABLE 4. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, [α -Amino acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$

Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)		35	40	45	50	55	Average
$k' \times 10^5 \text{ (sec.}^{-1}\text{)}$	A	9.80	12.8	15.2	19.4	25.0	—
	B	8.42	11.2	13.4	19.2	24.1	—
$k \times 10^5 \text{ (sec.}^{-1}\text{)}$	A	3.10	4.05	4.80	6.14	7.89	—
	B	6.69	8.90	10.6	15.3	19.1	—
$\Delta E^\ddagger \text{ (K.Cals./mole)}$	A	9.21	9.21	9.21	9.21	9.21	9.21
	B	10.5	10.5	10.5	10.5	10.5	10.5
$A' \times 10^{-2} \text{ (sec.}^{-1}\text{)}$	A	0.96	0.99	0.93	0.95	0.98	0.96
	B	16.8	17.1	15.6	17.5	17.0	16.8
$\Delta H^\ddagger \text{ (K.Cals./mole)}$	A	8.59	8.58	8.57	8.56	8.55	8.57
	B	9.88	9.87	9.86	9.85	9.84	9.86
$\Delta S^\ddagger \text{ (e.u.)}$	A	-50.7	-50.6	-50.9	-50.8	-50.7	-50.7
	B	-45.0	-44.9	-45.2	-44.8	-45.0	-44.9
$\Delta F^\ddagger \text{ (K.Cals./mole)}$	A	24.2	24.4	24.8	25.0	25.2	24.7
	B	23.7	23.9	24.2	24.3	24.6	24.1

A represents Phenylalanine at pH 11.50.

B represents Serine at pH 11.10.

Discussion

In an aqueous solution, chloramine-T hydrolyses¹⁴ giving a variety of products viz., *p*-toluenesulphochloramide, dichloramine-T, hypochlorite ion, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and sodium ion, the relative amount of each of these species depend upon the pH of the solution¹⁵. However, the former three are the active oxidising species of chloramine-T in addition to chloramine-T itself.

rate decreases with increase in pH, it is concluded that *p*-toluenesulphochloramide is the main oxidising species of chloramine-T in this case.

It is proposed that the α -amino acid molecule reacts in a slow and rate determining step with *p*-toluenesulphochloramide molecule forming an intermediate monochloro amino acid which in a subsequent fast step interacts with another molecule of *p*-toluenesulphochloramide yielding products. Thus

the species monochloroamino acid exists only for a brief period. The steps may be schematically represented as follows :

Application of steady treatment with reasonable approximation that $k_{-1}[\text{NaOH}] \gg 2k_2[\text{RCH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}]$, yields the rate law as

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{N NaCl}] = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{N NaCl}][\text{RCH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}]}{[\text{NaOH}]} \quad \dots (8)$$

which is consistent with the experimental observations.

To account for the deviation of order in hydroxide ion from -1 and a slight negative methanol effect, it is proposed that an insignificantly small fraction of the overall reaction proceeds through another path involving hypochlorite ion replacing *p*-toluenesulphochloramide in step (7) resulting in the rate law as

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{N NaCl}] = k' [\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{N NaCl}][\text{RCH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}] \quad \dots (9)$$

k' being a constant. The net outcome of the two reaction paths is a fractional inverse order in hydroxide ion concentration. The slight negative methanol effect accounts for the interaction between the negatively charged ion and dipole in this path.

Both the schemes with atleast one neutral molecule in the rate determining step satisfactorily agree with the negligible influence of ionic strength variations. Dakin's¹⁶ report of the formation of intermediate monochloro amino acid and nitrile formation on using two moles of chloramine-T is also in accord with the observed stoichiometry and identification of nitriles as the end product. Further, the reported^{5,9} mechanism of oxidation of some other α -amino acids (viz., glycine, alanine, valine and leucine) also supports the proposed mechanism.

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